

Effects of Road Infrastructure Development on Local Community Household Income: A Case study of Lusaka - Ndola Dual Carriage way Construction in Chibombo Area

Lungowe Anakoka¹ and Peter Silwimba^{2a}

¹School of Humanities and Business, Information and Communications University, Lusaka, Zambia

²Risk Department, National Savings and Credit Bank

^aSchool of Humanities and Business, Information and Communications University, Lusaka, Zambia

^aCorresponding Author: Peter Silwimba, Emailsilwimbap47@gmail.com

APA Citation and Referencing: Anakoka, A. & Silwimba, P. (2025). Examining the effects of Road Infrastructure Development on Nearly Households Income: A Case study of Lusaka - Ndola Dual Carriage way Construction in Chibombo Area. *JENER Journal of Empirical and Non-Empirical Research*, 1(3), 895-905

ARTICLE INFORMATION	ABSTRACT
<p>Article history: Published on 24th Dec 2025</p> <p>Keywords: Dual Carriageway Household Income Infrastructure Development</p>	<p>This study examined the effects of road infrastructure development on household income in Chibombo, Zambia, focusing on the Lusaka-Ndola Dual Carriageway construction. The specific objectives were to assess the influence of road infrastructure on access to income-generating activities, evaluate the relationship between road development and household income levels, and investigate the perceived benefits and challenges of the road project. A descriptive survey design utilizing a mixed-methods approach was adopted, with 100 households selected through stratified random sampling. Primary data were collected using a questionnaire, and data analysis was performed using Megastat. The study revealed that the Lusaka-Ndola dual carriage way road project has improved access to customers, with 76% of respondents reporting an increase. The road project has also attracted new buyers to the area (82%) and enabled respondents to travel easily to sell their goods/services (76%). The chi-square test showed a statistically significant association between improved road access and business income increase ($\chi^2 = 177.14$, $p = 0.00$). The study found that 64% of respondents reported an increase in household income since the road was constructed. The majority of respondents (70%) were able to diversify their income sources, and 64% believe that their household is now better off economically than before the road project. The hypothesis test results suggest that respondents tend to be neutral or slightly agree that their household income has increased since the road was constructed (mean = 2.230, $t = 1.73$, $p = 0.0437$). The study revealed that the road project has improved access to health facilities (100%), and 58% of respondents believe that safety has improved with the new road infrastructure. However, some challenges were reported, including concerns over displacement (18%) and limited improvement in school attendance (28%). The regression analysis showed a moderate positive relationship between the independent variables (percentage increase in access to health facilities and number of investments attracted) and the dependent variable (quality of life) ($R^2 = 0.329$, $F = 23.80$, $p = 3.89E-09$). The study concludes that the Lusaka-Ndola dual carriage way road project has had a positive impact on local livelihoods, with improvements in household income, access to health facilities, and economic opportunities.</p>

1. Introduction

1.1 Background

Road infrastructure is recognized as a key enabler of socio-economic development, globally. According to the World Bank (2020), improved road connectivity facilitates access to markets, reduces transportation costs, and enhances household income, especially in rural areas. In China and India, rural road development has led to significant increases in household incomes by improving access to inputs, outputs, and employment opportunities (Li et al., 2018). The World Economic Forum (2019) also highlights that efficient transportation networks promote mobility, regional integration, and economic empowerment of households.

In Africa, road infrastructure deficits continue to hinder development. The African Development Bank (AfDB, 2018) reports that inadequate rural roads reduce agricultural productivity and hinder access to basic services. Studies in Kenya and Ethiopia indicate that road improvements enhance household income by facilitating access to urban markets and reducing post-harvest losses

(Gachassin, Najman & Raballand, 2017). In Rwanda and Malawi, rural roads have been linked to increased agricultural income and expanded off-farm employment opportunities (Manda et al., 2021).

1.2 Problem Statement

Despite significant investment in road infrastructure most notably the Lusaka–Ndola Dual Carriageway it remains unclear how much this massive project has contributed to addressing persistent economic vulnerability and limited income growth among households in Chibombo District. Road infrastructure is widely regarded as a catalyst for economic development, with improved connectivity expected to enhance access to markets, employment, and essential services (World Bank, 2020; African Development Bank, 2021). However, the trickle-down effects of such large-scale projects are not uniformly distributed, particularly among rural populations (UN-Habitat, 2022).

1.3 Research Objectives

The general and specific objectives of this study are presented in the sections below.

1.3.1 General Objectives

To examine the effects of road infrastructure development on household income in the Chibombo area, using the Lusaka–Ndola Dual Carriageway construction as a case study.

Specific Objectives:

- i. To assess the influence of road infrastructure on access to income-generating activities among households in Chibombo.
- ii. To evaluate the relationship between road development and household income levels.
- iii. To investigate the perceived benefits and challenges of the Lusaka–Ndola road project on local livelihoods.

1.3.2 Research Questions

- i. How has road infrastructure influenced income-generating activities among households in Chibombo?
- ii. What is the relationship between road development and changes in household income levels?
- iii. What are the perceived socio-economic effects of the Lusaka–Ndola Dual Carriageway on nearby communities?

1.5 Theoretical Framework

This study is anchored on the infrastructure-Led Development Theory, which emphasizes the pivotal role of infrastructure investment as a catalyst for economic growth and socio-economic transformation. Aschauer (1989) initially posited that public investment in infrastructure such as roads, energy, and communication networks directly enhances economic productivity by reducing production and transaction costs. Subsequently, Calderón and Servén (2010) expanded on this idea, highlighting that infrastructure improvements generate direct, indirect, and induced multiplier effects, including employment creation, income growth, and poverty reduction.

In rural settings, road infrastructure is especially critical for connecting remote communities to larger markets, health services, education facilities, and employment centers (Straub, 2011). By reducing travel time and transportation costs, roads facilitate agricultural commercialization, enable diversification of income sources, and improve access to social services (Fay & Yepes, 2003; Canning & Pedroni, 2008). This linkage is vital in Sub-Saharan Africa, where inadequate infrastructure remains a key constraint to rural development (Calderón & Servén, 2014; African Development Bank, 2018).

The Lusaka–Ndola Dual Carriageway represents a strategic infrastructure investment intended to unlock economic potential in adjacent rural areas such as Chibombo District. According to Gramlich (1994), well-planned infrastructure projects can trigger broad-based economic benefits by enhancing market integration and labor mobility. Improved road networks reduce spatial barriers, fostering regional development and enabling households to participate more fully in formal economic activities (World Bank, 2020; Manda et al., 2021).

Furthermore, infrastructure investments contribute to human capital development by improving access to schools and healthcare services, which in turn positively influence long-term income prospects (Aschauer, 2000; Calderón & Servén, 2010). The multiplier effects also extend to informal sectors, where improved connectivity encourages entrepreneurship and income diversification (Straub, 2011; African Development Bank, 2018).

By applying the infrastructure-Led Development Theory, this study seeks to analyze how road infrastructure projects like the Lusaka–Ndola Dual Carriageway impact household income and employment in Chibombo. The theory provides a comprehensive framework for understanding the mechanisms through which infrastructure stimulates economic activity, improves livelihoods, and contributes to national development goals (World Bank, 2020; Calderón & Servén, 2014).

1.6 Significance of the Study

This study is significant in that it contributes to the growing body of literature on infrastructure and rural development by offering localized, empirical evidence on the impact of road infrastructure on household income in Zambia. Although previous research has explored infrastructure development in general (Calderón & Servén, 2010; Foster & Briceño-Garmendia, 2010), there is limited focus on how major road projects affect rural communities at the household level. By focusing on the Lusaka–Ndola Dual Carriageway and its effects on Chibombo District, this research provides context-specific data that enhances understanding of infrastructure's role in improving economic outcomes in underdeveloped rural settings. Such evidence is essential for refining development theories and adapting them to local realities in sub-Saharan Africa (World Bank, 2020).

2. Literature Review

This chapter presents a thematic review of existing literature based on the study objectives. It draws from global, regional, and local sources to provide insights into how road infrastructure affects household income. The themes align with each specific objective of the study. The chapter concludes with a critique of the literature and identification of research gaps.

2.1 Literature Review on Objective One-Awareness in Chibombo.

Access to road infrastructure is universally acknowledged as a fundamental enabler of economic development and poverty reduction (World Bank, 2010; Gwilliam, 2011). Globally, transport networks, particularly road systems, have been found to play a pivotal role in facilitating trade, enhancing labor mobility, and improving access to essential services such as education and healthcare (Banerjee, Duflo & Qian, 2012; Estache & Fay, 2007). Roads serve as physical links between rural and urban areas, allowing for the movement of goods, services, and people, which in turn creates opportunities for income generation, employment, and market participation (Bryceson et al., 2008; Porter, 2014). According to Calderón and Servén (2015), improved road networks reduce travel time and transportation costs, enabling rural households to access wider markets, increase their productivity, and diversify income sources. This underscores the transformative power of road infrastructure as an instrument of inclusive economic growth (Fan, Nyange & Rao, 2005; Gachassin, Najman & Raballand, 2010).

One of the most well-documented global examples is the Pradhan Mantri Gram Sadak Yojana (PMGSY) in India, a nationwide rural roads program launched in 2000. The PMGSY aimed to provide all-weather road connectivity to unconnected rural habitations (Government of India, 2016). Empirical evaluations of the program show that it significantly improved non-farm employment in connected villages. Asher and Novosad (2020) found that rural communities benefiting from the program experienced a 10–15% increase in non-farm employment opportunities. The improvement in transportation not only reduced isolation but also allowed rural labor to engage in more productive off-farm activities, including trade, services, and manufacturing (Lokshin & Yemtsov, 2005). Additionally, the increased ease of movement facilitated school attendance and access to healthcare, thereby indirectly supporting long-term income growth through human capital development (Ali & Pernia, 2003; Jalan & Ravallion, 2002).

2.2 Literature Review on Objective Two-Perceived Challenges

The relationship between road infrastructure development and household income has been extensively documented across various global contexts. In developing and emerging economies, investments in road infrastructure have consistently led to significant improvements in household earnings by enhancing connectivity, reducing transaction costs, and increasing labor productivity (Fan & Rao, 2003; Estache & Garsous, 2012; Hettige, 2006). These improvements facilitate access to markets, employment opportunities, and essential services, thereby contributing to economic upliftment and poverty reduction (Khandker, Bakht, & Koolwal, 2009; Dorosh, Wang, & You, 2012).

In China, the expansion of road infrastructure has played a pivotal role in economic growth and poverty alleviation. Fan and Chan-Kang (2005) conducted a comprehensive study evaluating the contribution of roads to economic growth and poverty reduction. Their findings indicate that investments in low-quality (mostly rural) roads yielded benefit-cost ratios for national GDP that were about four times larger than those for high-quality roads. Moreover, these rural roads were more effective in reducing poverty, raising more rural and urban poor above the poverty line per yuan invested compared to high-quality roads. This underscores the significant impact of rural road development on household income and poverty reduction in China (Fan, Zhang & Zhang, 2002; World Bank, 2010). Similar conclusions were drawn by Chen and Ravallion (2007), who highlighted that rural infrastructure is closely linked with improvements in household consumption and poverty metrics in rural China.

2.3 Literature Review on Objective Three-Adequacy Level of National grid

Road infrastructure development, while primarily associated with economic growth and income generation, also profoundly influences the socio-economic fabric of households and communities worldwide. Contemporary research and development discourse increasingly recognize that the impacts of road projects transcend measurable economic outcomes and encompass changes in social inclusion, access to essential services, perceptions of governance, and overall well-being (World Bank, 2020; Porter, 2014; Calderón & Servén, 2015). The multidimensional perceptions of road infrastructure reflect how communities interpret and experience such projects in ways that shape their attitudes, behaviors, and long-term developmental trajectories (Nsengiyumva et al., 2020).

The World Economic Forum (2019) emphasizes that infrastructure development plays a critical role in reshaping social interaction patterns. Roads facilitate physical connectivity that not only links markets and services but also enhances interpersonal relationships and community networks. Mu and van de Walle (2011) provide empirical evidence from Vietnam, demonstrating that rural road construction significantly improved social inclusion among marginalized groups. By connecting isolated hamlets to town centers, roads enabled community members to participate more actively in local governance, social events, and cooperative groups. This access reduced social isolation, particularly among women and the elderly, who otherwise faced mobility constraints (Asher & Novosad, 2020).

3. Methodology

This chapter outlines the methodological framework that guides this study investigating the effects of good infrastructure on household income and employment in Chibombo District. The chapter details the research design, target population, sampling procedures, data collection methods, and analysis techniques. Emphasis is placed on ensuring the reliability and validity of the

study, while maintaining alignment with the stated research objectives. The mixed-methods approach adopted facilitates a comprehensive understanding of both the quantitative outcomes and qualitative experiences associated with infrastructural developments in the study area.

3.1 Research Design

This study will adopt a descriptive survey design utilizing a mixed-methods approach, incorporating both quantitative and qualitative data collection and analysis. The descriptive survey design is well-suited for this investigation as it allows the researcher to systematically describe the current state of infrastructure and its socio-economic impacts on households within Chibombo District (Creswell, 2018). By combining quantitative techniques such as structured questionnaires that generate measurable data on income and employment patterns with qualitative methods such as semi-structured interviews capturing nuanced perspectives the study achieves data triangulation, which enhances the robustness and depth of findings (Tashakkori & Teddlie, 2010). This approach not only quantifies effects but also explores the underlying mechanisms and community experiences associated with infrastructural change.

3.2 Target Population

The target population comprises all households residing in Chibombo District who are directly or indirectly impacted by infrastructure projects, including road networks, electrification, and water supply systems. According to the Central Statistical Office (2023), Chibombo has an estimated 10,000 households spread across diverse wards, reflecting varied levels of infrastructure access. Besides households, key informants such as local government officials, ward councilors, and project implementers form an essential segment of the population to provide institutional and operational insights into infrastructure development and its socio-economic outcomes.

3.3 Sampling Design

To ensure representativeness and minimize sampling bias, a random sampling technique will be used. The population will be divided based on key characteristics such as geographical location (e.g., proximity to main roads or infrastructure nodes) and degree of infrastructure access (high, medium, low). This stratification recognizes the heterogeneous nature of Chibombo District and ensures that various community segments, including both well-served and underserved areas, are adequately represented. Within each stratum, households will be randomly selected using a lottery method or random number generation, allowing each household an equal chance of inclusion (Kothari, 2004). This method increases the precision of estimates by reducing sampling error and supports subgroup comparisons across different infrastructure conditions.

3.4 Sample Size Determination

The sample size will be determined using Taro Yamane's formula (1967) for finite populations:

Thus, the final sample size was rounded to 100 households, which were randomly selected from the stratified population. This sample size reflects a balance between logistical feasibility and the need for reliable data, allowing for generalizable inferences about the broader population while maintaining control over sampling error (Israel, 1992).

In addition, purposive sampling will be used to select approximately 15 to 20 key informants for in-depth interviews. These will include local leaders, government officials, project managers, and other knowledgeable stakeholders, thereby enriching the data with expert insights relevant to the research objectives.

3.5 Data Collection Methods

Data collection will involve both quantitative and qualitative instruments to comprehensively capture the effects of infrastructure. **Structured Questionnaires:** These will be administered to the selected households. The questionnaires will consist of both closed-ended questions (e.g., Likert scales, multiple-choice) to quantify variables such as household income levels, employment status, frequency of infrastructure usage, and access to services, and open-ended questions to capture additional explanations or personal experiences. The questionnaires will be pilot-tested on a small subset of respondents to ensure clarity, validity, and cultural appropriateness.

Semi-Structured Interviews: Key informant interviews will be conducted with local government officials, project implementers, and community leaders. The interviews will explore themes such as the planning and implementation of infrastructure projects, perceived benefits and challenges, and community engagement processes. This qualitative method allows for flexibility to probe deeper into issues and gain rich, contextual insights (Patton, 2015).

Document Review: Relevant government reports, project documents, and demographic data will be reviewed to supplement primary data, provide background, and validate findings.

3.6 Data Analysis

Quantitative Analysis: Data from questionnaires will be coded and entered into SPSS for statistical analysis. Descriptive statistics such as frequencies, means, and percentages will summarize demographic profiles and access patterns. Inferential statistics, including chi-square tests for association between categorical variables (e.g., infrastructure access and employment status) and Pearson's correlation to assess relationships between continuous variables (e.g., road access and household income), will be performed. Where appropriate, regression analysis may be used to control for confounding factors.

Qualitative Analysis: Interview transcripts and open-ended questionnaire responses will be transcribed and analyzed thematically. Using NVivo or manual coding, data will be organized into themes reflecting community perceptions, challenges, and socio-

economic impacts. Themes will be iteratively refined to identify patterns and divergences that illuminate how infrastructure influences livelihoods (Braun & Clarke, 2006).

3.7 Triangulation

Triangulation will be employed to enhance the credibility of the findings. Data collected through surveys, interviews, and document reviews will be cross-verified to ensure consistency and validity of the results. This process strengthens the study by integrating multiple perspectives.

3.8 Limitations of the Study

Some potential limitations include the inaccessibility of certain rural households due to terrain, respondent reluctance due to privacy concerns, and possible data inaccuracies arising from self-reporting. These challenges will be mitigated by training enumerators, pre-testing instruments, and assuring participants of confidentiality.

3.9 Ethical Considerations

The study will adhere to ethical guidelines including informed consent, voluntary participation, and data confidentiality. Approval will be sought from the university’s ethics review board, and participants will be briefed on the purpose of the research and their right to withdraw at any time without consequences.

4. Research Results

This chapter presented the findings of the study per thematic area which are in tables and graphs. Furthermore, the chapter discussed the research findings of this study. The main purpose of the study was to examine the effects of road infrastructure development on household income in the Chibombo area, focusing on the Lusaka-Ndola Dual Carriage way construction. This chapter is divided into three sections. The first section begins by giving background information of the respondents while the second part is a presentation and the third part discusses the research findings in relation to the research objectives of the study.

4.1 Demographic Characteristics of Respondents

The demographic characteristics of the respondents included, Gender, Age group, Marital Status, Education Level, Household Size, and Length of residence in the community.

4.1.1 Gender of the respondents

Figure 4.1 below is the representation of respondents according to the gender.

Figure 4.1 Gender

The data above in figure 4.1, shows that out of the total respondents, 58% are male and 42% are female. This indicates that the majority of the respondents were male, suggesting a slightly skewed gender distribution in the sample.

4.1.2 Household Size

Figure 4.2 below is a representation of the respondents according to the Household Size

Figure 4.2 household size

The data shows that the majority of households (54%) have 4-6 members, indicating that most households are relatively large. A significant proportion (40%) have 1-3 members, suggesting a smaller but still notable presence of smaller households. Households with 7 or more members are relatively rare, accounting for only 6% of the sample. This suggests that large extended families are not common in the sample population.

4.2 Objective One- Influence of Road Infrastructure on Income-Generating Activities

With regard to this objective the following question's responses have been presented: The Lusaka -Ndola road has improved my access to customers, I am now able to travel easily to sell my goods/services, Improved road access has helped me start a new business, What is the Competition percentage increase as result of the Construction of the new road, What is the business income percentage increase as result of the Construction of the new road, The road project has attracted new buyers to the area, and The road has enabled me to transport farm produce to urban markets.

4.2.1 The Lusaka -Ndola dual carriage way road has improved my access to customers

Figure 4.3 below shows the responses when respondents were asked to state whether Lusaka Ndola dual carriage way improved access to customers

Figure 4.3 improved my access to customers

The data shows that the majority of respondents (76%) believe that the Lusaka-Ndola dual carriage way has improved their access to customers, with 40% strongly agreeing and 36% agreeing. A moderate proportion (18%) are neutral, while a small percentage (6%) disagree. Notably, no respondents strongly disagree, indicating a generally positive perception of the road's impact on customer access. This suggests that the improved road infrastructure is likely to have a beneficial effect on local businesses and economic activity.

4.2.2 I am now able to travel easily to sell my goods/services

The respondents were asked whether the road construction attracted more customers, expanding markets and boosting trade volumes. The following results are shown in figure 4.4 below.

Figure 4.4 Improve Road access has helped you start a new business

The data indicates that the majority of respondents (76%) believe that they are now able to travel easily to sell their goods/services, with 30% strongly agreeing and 46% agreeing. A small proportion (6%) are neutral. However, 18% of respondents disagree, with 12% disagreeing and 6% strongly disagreeing, suggesting that some individuals still face challenges in

traveling to sell their goods/services. Overall, the data suggests that there has been an improvement in mobility for many respondents, likely due to the improved road infrastructure.

4.2.3 A chi-square test

Table 1 below shows the chi-square test of Significance

Improved road access has helped me start a new business	What is the business income percentage increase as result						Total
	Less than 20%	20 - 30%	30 - 40%	40 - 50%	More than 50%	none	
strongly agree	6	6	14	12	6		44
agree		12	20				32
Neutral	6						6
Disagree						12	12
Strongly Disagree						6	6
Total	12	18	34	12	6	18	100
177.14 chi-square 20 df 0.00 p-value							

The cross-tabulation suggests a possible relationship between improved road access helping to start a new business and business income percentage increase. Among those who strongly agree that improved road access helped start a new business, 6% reported a less than 20% income increase, 6% reported a 20-30% increase, 14% reported a 30-40% increase, 12% reported a 40-50% increase, and 6% reported more than 50% increase.

The chi-square value of 177.14 with 20 degrees of freedom and a p-value of 0.00 indicates a statistically significant association between the two variables. This suggests that improved road access has a significant impact on business income increase, and the relationship is unlikely to be due to chance. The strong association is likely driven by the improved access to markets, customers, and resources facilitated by the new road.

4.3 To Evaluate The Relationship Between Road Development And Household Income Levels In Chibombo.

4.3.1 Household income has increased since the road was constructed

Figure 4.5 indicate the results from the respondents when they were asked to state whether their income has increased due to road in their area.

Figure 4.5 Household income has increased since the road was constructed

The data above shows that the majority of respondents (64%) believe that their household income has increased since the road was constructed, with 43% strongly agreeing and 21% agreeing. A small proportion (12%) are neutral, while 24% disagree, with 18% disagreeing and 6% strongly disagreeing. This suggests that the road construction has had a positive impact on household income for many respondents, likely due to improved access to markets, employment opportunities, and other economic benefits.

4.3.2 What is the percentage increase of household food Security as a result of construction of the new road

Figure 4.6 below shows the results from the respondents when they were engaged to indicate the percentage increase of their household food security as a result of construction of the to their localities.

Figure 4.6 Household food Security as a result of construction of the new road

The data in figure 4.16 above reveals that 36% of respondents reported no increase in household food security as a result of the new road construction. Among those who reported an increase, 28% experienced a 16-20% increase, followed by 24% who experienced an 11-15% increase, and 12% who experienced a 6-10% increase. Notably, no respondents reported an increase of 1-5%. This suggests that the new road has had a moderate to significant positive impact on household food security for many respondents, likely due to improved access to markets and food supplies.

4.3.5 Hypothesis Test: Mean vs. Hypothesized Value

Table 2 below shows the hypothesis test for mean vs hypothesis

Hypothesis Test: Mean vs. Hypothesized Value	
2.000	hypothesized value
2.230	mean Household income has increased since the road was constructed
1.332	std. dev.
0.133	std. error
100	n
99	df
1.73	t
.0437	p-value (one-tailed, upper)

The hypothesized value of 2.000 represents the expected mean value of the response to the statement "Household income has increased since the road was constructed", assuming that respondents tend to disagree with the statement. In other words, the null hypothesis is that the mean response is 2, indicating disagreement. The actual mean response is 2.230, which is higher than the hypothesized value of 2.000. This suggests that, on average, respondents tend to be neutral or slightly agree that their household income has increased since the road was constructed.

The t-statistic is 1.73, indicating that the observed mean is higher than the hypothesized value. The p-value is 0.0437, which is less than the typical significance level of 0.05. This means that we reject the null hypothesis that the mean response is equal to 2.000, and conclude that the mean response is statistically significantly higher than 2.000. In conclusion, the data suggests that respondents tend to be neutral or slightly agree that their household income has increased since the road was constructed, indicating a slight positive impact of the road construction on household income.

4.4 The benefits and challenges of the Lusaka-Ndola dual carriage road project on local livelihoods in chibombo

4.4.1 The percentage increase access to health facilities as a result of newly constructed road.

Figure 4.7 below shows the percentage at which health facilities access increased to newly constructed road.

Figure 4.7 Increased access to health facilities as a result of newly constructed road

The data shows that all respondents (100%) reported an increase in access to health facilities as a result of the newly constructed road. The majority (42%) reported a 26-50% increase, followed by 28% who reported a 51-75% increase, and 24% who reported a 0-25% increase. Additionally, 6% of respondents reported a 76-100% increase. This suggests that the new road has significantly improved access to health facilities for the respondents, likely due to reduced travel time and increased mobility.

4.3.2 The number of investments attracted to the community as a result of the newly constructed road

Figure 4.8 Investments attracted to the community as a result of the newly constructed road

The data shows that 51% of respondents reported that 0-1 investments have been attracted to the community as a result of the newly constructed road, indicating a relatively low level of investment attraction. A quarter (25%) reported 2-5 investments, while 12% reported 6-10 investments. Notably, no respondents reported 11-20 investments, and 12% reported no investments at all. This suggests that while the new road may have had some positive impact on investment attraction, the overall effect has been limited, and more efforts may be needed to attract significant investment to the community.

4.4.4 Regression Analysis test for significant

Table 3 below shows the regression analysis test of Significance

Regression Analysis						
		R ² 0.329		n 100		
		Adjusted R ² 0.315		k 2		
		R 0.574		Dep. Var.		The quality of life has generally improved in the community
		Std. Error 0.980				
ANOVA table						
Source	SS	df	MS	F	p-value	
Regression	45.6771	2	22.8385	23.80	0.00	
Residual	93.0729	97	0.9595			
Total	138.7500	99				
Regression output						
variables	coefficients	std. error	t (df=97)	p-value	confidence interval	
Intercept	1.4086	0.3508	4.015	.0001	0.7124	2.1048
The percentage increase access to health facilities as a result of newly constructed road	0.0091	0.1194	0.076	.9395	-0.2280	0.2462
Number of investments attracted to the community as a result of the newly constructed road	0.5187	0.0783	6.624	0.00	0.3633	0.6741

The regression analysis reveals a moderate positive relationship between the independent variables (percentage increase in access to health facilities and number of investments attracted) and the dependent variable (quality of life). The R² value of 0.329 indicates that approximately 32.9% of the variation in quality of life can be explained by the two independent variables. The adjusted R² value of 0.315 suggests that the model is a reasonable fit, considering the number of predictors.

The ANOVA table shows that the regression model is statistically significant (F = 23.80, p-value = 3.89E-09), indicating that the independent variables collectively explain a significant portion of the variation in quality of life.

The correlation coefficient (R = 0.574) indicates a moderate positive correlation between the independent variables and quality of life. Specifically, the number of investments attracted to the community has a significant positive relationship with quality of life (coefficient = 0.5187, p-value = 1.95E-09), suggesting that an increase in investments is associated with an improvement in quality of life. However, the percentage increase in access to health facilities does not have a statistically significant relationship with quality of life (coefficient = 0.0091, p-value = 0.9395).

The results suggest that the number of investments attracted to the community is a stronger predictor of quality of life, while the percentage increase in access to health facilities does not have a significant impact on quality of life. This may indicate that economic opportunities and investments have a more direct influence on quality of life, whereas access to health facilities may be a necessary but not sufficient condition for improving quality of life.

4.5 Discussion of the Findings

4.5.1 Demographic characteristics of the respondents

The demographic characteristics of the respondents in this study reveal some interesting findings. In terms of gender, the sample is slightly skewed towards males, with 58% male and 42% female respondents. This is consistent with other studies in Zambia, which have also reported a slightly higher participation of males in surveys and research studies (Central Statistical Office, 2015). However, the difference is not drastic, suggesting that the sample is generally representative of the population in terms of gender. The age group distribution of the respondents is predominantly young to middle-aged, with 37% of respondents falling within the 26-35 age group and 33% within the 18-25 age group. This is consistent with Zambia's youthful population, where the median age is around 17 years (World Bank, 2020). Other studies in Zambia have also reported a similar age distribution, highlighting the importance of targeting this demographic in research and development initiatives (Lusaka District Health Office, 2018).

4.5.2 Influence of Road Infrastructure on Income-Generating Activities in Chibombo

The findings of this study suggest that the Lusaka-Ndola road has had a significant positive impact on income-generating activities in Chibombo District, Zambia. The majority of respondents (76%) believe that the road has improved their access to customers, and 76% report that they are now able to travel easily to sell their goods/services. This is consistent with global literature, which highlights the role of road infrastructure in facilitating trade, enhancing labor mobility, and improving access to essential services (World Bank, 2010; Gwilliam, 2011).

The study also finds that improved road access has helped start new businesses, with 76% of respondents reporting that it has had a positive impact on their entrepreneurship endeavors. This aligns with findings from other countries, such as India, where the Pradhan Mantri Gram Sadak Yojana (PMGSY) program improved non-farm employment opportunities (Asher & Novosad, 2020), and Vietnam, where the Vietnam Rural Transport Project (VRTP) increased income generation among rural households (Mu & van de Walle, 2011).

4.5.3 The relationship between road development and household income levels in Chibombo.

The findings of this study suggest that the road construction has had a positive impact on household income levels in Chibombo, Zambia. The majority of respondents (64%) believe that their household income has increased since the road was constructed, with 43% strongly agreeing and 21% agreeing. This is consistent with global literature, which highlights the role of road infrastructure in facilitating economic growth, reducing poverty, and improving household income (Fan & Rao, 2003; Estache & Garsous, 2012; Hettige, 2006). The study also finds that the road construction has led to improved food security, with 28% of respondents experiencing a 16-20% increase in household food security. This is likely due to improved access to markets and food supplies, as well as increased economic opportunities (Dercon et al., 2009; Gibson & Rozelle, 2003).

4.5.4 The Benefits and Challenges Of The Lusaka-Ndola Road Project On Local Livelihoods In Chibombo

The findings suggest that the Lusaka-Ndola Road project has had a positive impact on local livelihoods in Chibombo, Zambia. The majority of respondents (64%) believe that the quality of life has generally improved in the community, with improved access to health facilities (100%), increased social interactions (57%), and better access to government and public services (33%).

The regression analysis reveals a moderate positive relationship between the independent variables (percentage increase in access to health facilities and number of investments attracted) and the dependent variable (quality of life). The number of investments attracted to the community has a significant positive relationship with quality of life, suggesting that economic opportunities and investments have a more direct influence on quality of life.

5. Recommendation and Conclusion

This chapter presents the conclusion and recommendations of the study on the effects of road infrastructure development on household income in the Chibombo area, using the Lusaka-Ndola Dual Carriageway construction as a case study. The study aimed to assess the influence of road infrastructure on access to income-generating activities among households in Chibombo, evaluate the relationship between road development and household income levels, and investigate the perceived benefits and challenges of the Lusaka – Ndola dual carriage way road project on local livelihoods.

5.1 Conclusion

The study concludes that the Lusaka-Ndola dual carriage way road project has had a positive impact on local livelihoods in Chibombo, Zambia. The improved road infrastructure has increased access to customers, attracted new buyers, and enabled respondents to travel easily to sell their goods and services. The road project has also improved household income, access to health facilities, and safety. However, some challenges were reported, including concerns over displacement and limited improvement in school attendance. The study highlights the importance of considering social and economic impacts in road infrastructure development and recommends that policymakers prioritize inclusive and participatory approaches to maximize benefits and minimize social costs.

5.2 Recommendation

Based on the research findings, the following recommendations are made:

1. **Inclusive Planning and Implementation:** Ensure that local communities are involved in the planning and implementation of road infrastructure projects to address concerns over displacement and ensure that benefits are equitably distributed.
2. **Investment in Social Services:** Invest in social services such as education and healthcare to address the limited improvement in school attendance and leverage the improved road infrastructure to enhance education outcomes.

3. Promote Economic Opportunities: Promote economic opportunities and investments in the area to maximize the benefits of improved road infrastructure and enhance quality of life.
4. Monitor and Evaluate: Regularly monitor and evaluate the impact of road infrastructure projects on local livelihoods to identify areas for improvement and ensure that benefits are sustained.
5. Address Displacement Concerns: Address concerns over displacement by providing fair compensation and support to affected households and ensuring that the construction process is managed fairly and transparently.

References

- [1] Alhassan, I. (2016). Rural roads and economic activities in Ghana: Evidence from Northern Region. *International Journal of Development Research*, 6(10), 9723–9732.
- [2] Asian Development Bank. (2017). Infrastructure development and poverty reduction. *ADB Working Paper Series*.
- [3] Banerjee, A., Duflo, E., & Qian, N. (2020). On the road: Access to transportation infrastructure and economic development. *American Economic Review*, 110(10), 3267–3299.
- [4] Calderón, C., & Servén, L. (2010). Infrastructure, growth, and inequality in Africa. *World Bank Policy Research Working Paper*, No. 5612.
- [5] Central Statistical Office. (2023). Zambia population and housing census report. Lusaka: CSO.
- [6] Chileshe, M., & Mwape, S. (2020). Socio-economic impacts of road displacement in Chibombo. *Zambia Social Science Journal*, 8(1), 45–59.
- [7] Eboh, E. C., & Anyanwu, C. M. (2017). Road infrastructure and social mobility in rural Nigeria. *Journal of Infrastructure Development*, 9(1), 1–18.
- [8] Fan, S., Zhang, X., & Rao, N. (2004). Public expenditure, growth, and poverty reduction in rural China. *American Journal of Agricultural Economics*, 86(5), 1332–1340.
- [9] Foster, V., & Briceño-Garmendia, C. (2010). Africa's infrastructure: Building access for growth and development. *World Bank*.
- [10] Gramlich, E. M. (1994). Infrastructure investment: A review essay. *Journal of Economic Literature*, 32(3), 1176–1196.
- [11] Gwilliam, K. (2008). Urban transport in developing countries. *Transport Reviews*, 28(5), 551–567.
- [12] Khandker, S. R., Bakht, Z., & Koolwal, G. B. (2009). The poverty impact of rural roads: Evidence from Bangladesh. *Economic Development and Cultural Change*, 57(4), 685–722.
- [13] Kunda, B., & Nkonde, C. (2021). The role of infrastructure in poverty reduction in Zambia. *Zambia Economic Review*, 7(4), 101–117.
- [14] Mberengwa, T., & Dzvimbo, E. (2017). Rural road infrastructure and poverty reduction in Zimbabwe. *African Journal of Rural Development*, 2(1), 56–65.
- [15] Ministry of Infrastructure and Housing. (2022). Community engagement survey report: Lusaka-Ndola Dual Carriageway project. Lusaka: Government Printer.
- [16] Ministry of Transport and Communications. (2019). National infrastructure development strategy: Zambia. Lusaka: Government Printer.
- [17] Mwansa, M., & Banda, T. (2017). Water supply infrastructure and women's livelihoods in rural Zambia. *Development in Practice*, 27(6), 820–832.
- [18] Nsengiyumva, J. B., et al. (2020). Community perceptions on road rehabilitation in Rwanda. *Journal of Development Studies*, 56(3), 422–438.
- [19] Ochieng, E. G., & Bett, G. K. (2017). Effects of road infrastructure on household income in Kenya. *International Journal of Economics and Finance*, 9(7), 104–113.
- [20] Odhiambo, N. M., & K'Akumu, O. A. (2020). Impact of Thika Superhighway on local business in Kenya. *African Urban Studies*, 12(4), 359–375.
- [21] Phiri, P., & Tembo, G. (2019). Infrastructure access and educational outcomes in Eastern Province, Zambia. *Journal of African Education*, 11(1), 33–47.
- [22] Porter, G. (2014). Transport services and their impact on rural livelihoods in Africa. *Transport Reviews*, 34(1), 25–45.
- [23] Sichinga, A. (2019). Transportation infrastructure and agricultural marketing in Zambia. *Journal of African Agricultural Economics*, 10(2), 58–73.
- [24] Tembo, J. (2018). Rural electrification and household income in Central Province. *Zambian Journal of Economic Development*, 4(3), 22–35.
- [25] World Bank. (2013). Jobs and growth: Analytical framework for infrastructure-led development. Washington, DC: World Bank.
- [26] World Bank. (2014). *World development report 2014: Risk and opportunity – Managing risk for development*. Washington, DC: World Bank.
- [27] World Bank. (2018). *Improving infrastructure in Africa: A regional perspective*. Washington, DC: World Bank.
- [28] Zulu, M., & Kalumba, K. (2020). Public perceptions of the Link Zambia 8000 road program. *Zambian Journal of Development Studies*, 5(2), 12–28.